

The first part of this study describes a technique by which the source parameters of an earthquake can be obtained from the spectrum of compressional waves. The source parameters defined are fault length, fracture velocity, and fault plane attitude. Two large, deep earthquakes are examined using this technique. The source parameters determined compare favorably with those obtained previously using different techniques. In the second section a method is proposed for discrimination between underground explosions and earthquakes. The technique utilizes the ratio of the spectrums of the two classes of events where the path of propagation is common to both. On the basis of the analysis of the SHOAL event and a nearby shallow earthquake it appears that the duration as determined from the spectral ratio is almost 10 times smaller for an explosion than it is for a comparable earthquake.